

X.P.E. DRAFT

REPORT

NEXUS PROTEIN ENGINEER
X.P.E. Copyright Nov 2001

V 1.0

What is X.P.E. ?

- > Stands for Nexus Protein Engineer
- > Project aims to provide real-time modelling of protein molecules
- > Currently -> Trial of natural proteins
- > Designer Protein

Note: - Nexus meaning connection point, collective union.

Background: Basics

-> The Cell

-> Coded using DNA

-> Amino Acid Components form

-> Protein, one of life's basic structures

Background: At The Factory Floor...

Protein: Result is a structure useful to cell operation and structure

The Cell

Background: Protein...

-> Structural use...

hair, nails, blood, muscle tissue,
skin, general cell structure...

-> Functional use...

Enzymes, metabolism, digestion...

-> Immune system identification of
cell types, e.g., cancer

helix_up.tif @ 100% (RGB)

helix_dens.tif @ 100% (RGB)

THE PAST

Computer Modelling

- > Proteins self-assemble in a real-time environment
- > Visual representation of molecule assemblies on computer screen
- > User enters Amino Acid sequence via keyboard

XPE

Splash

Screen:

XPE v1.0 Interface:

XPE Nexus Protein Engineer

File Options Export Project Help

Nexus Protein Engineer 1.0

Acids

- A - Ala
- C - Cys
- D - Asp
- E - Glu
- F - Phe
- G - Gly
- H - His
- I - Ile
- K - Lys
- L - Leu
- M - Met
- N - Asn
- P - Pro
- Q - Gln
- R - Arg
- S - Ser
- T - Thr
- V - Val
- W - Trp
- Y - Tyr

Fast Key

THE FUTURE

pH Select

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14

7.40

Set pH

Auto Rotate Reset

Zoom In Zoom Out

Save

Eject

Imagine the perfect world...

- > Elimination of Cancer
- > Fighting A.I.D.s
- > Eradication of Influenza
- > Cleaning up Oil Spills
- > Extending Life Expectancy
- > Unlimited Energy

This is the world that I propose.

The Request:

- > Four weeks full time wage at \$200 p/week
- > Computing Equipment at \$1200

Total Funding Request: \$2000

...the perfect
world...

Thank You.